

Polarisation Behaviour of Mild Steel in Sulphuric Acid Solutions containing Sodium Azide

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The polarisation behaviour of iron in deoxygenated sulphuric acid solutions in absence and presence of NaN_3 was studied. The presence of NaN_3 was found to shift the cathodic branches of the polarisation curves much more than the anodic ones to higher current densities. The cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes in absence and presence of NaN_3 were found to be the same. The corrosion rate and corrosion potential (shifting to more positive values) were found to increase with increasing NaN_3 concentration. It is assumed that the hydrazoic acid which results from the acid hydrolysis of NaN_3 undergoes reduction together with hydrogen evolution either under open-circuit conditions on the expense of iron dissolution or during the cathodic polarisation. The rate of hydrazoic acid reduction was found to depend on the concentration of both NaN_3 and H^+ ions. The presence of NaN_3 was also found to increase the anodic current in the active-passive transition and the passivation regions.

THE electrochemical behaviour and the dissolution kinetics of iron in acid solutions have been the subject to extensive studies¹⁻²⁰. The effect of ions on its dissolution kinetics especially the chloride ions are of special interest^{3,5-10}. Many investigators assumed the adsorption and contribution of halide ions beside OH^- ions during the metal dissolution^{3,5-10}. On the other hand, the role of an anion like the azide ion which behaves like halide ions in various aspects²¹⁻²³ on the iron dissolution seems to have drawn no attention so far. The electrochemical behaviour of azide ion at the dropping mercury electrode was studied by Moussa *et al.*^{24,25}. They found that the azide ion is specifically adsorbed on Hg surface through the positive branch of the electrocapillary curve and the adsorbability of the azide ion is intermediate between those of chloride and bromide ions²⁴. Harsch⁹ reported the corrosion behaviour of some ferrous materials in NaN_3 solutions in absence and presence of chloride ions. Incorporation of alkali metal azides in anti-corrosion solutions has been reviewed by Mason²⁷. The inhibition properties of azide ions towards corrosion in acid solutions, however, seem to have attracted very little attention.

The aim of the present work is to explore the effect of azide species on the polarisation behaviour of mild steel in sulphuric acid solutions.

Experimental

The electrodes were prepared from a 0.2 mm thick mild steel sheet having the following composition: C, 0.003; Mn, 0.28; P, 0.02; S, 0.022; Ni, 0.00; O, 0.033; Cu, 0.03% and Fe, remainder.

The electrodes were abraded using successively finer grades of emery papers until they became mirror bright and then washed with double-distilled water, degreased in benzene, ether and finally dried by a jet of air. The solutions were prepared using AnalaR grade chemicals and double-distilled water. Before each experiment, the test solution was deoxygenated by bubbling purified hydrogen gas for 2 h. Polarisation measurements were made using an electronic potentiostat¹⁶ and the steady current/potential relations were constructed. All experiments were conducted at 25° under hydrogen atmosphere.

Results and Discussion

The steady corrosion potential (E_{corr}) of mild steel in 1.0 and 0.1 N H_2SO_4 solutions was found to shift to more positive values in presence of NaN_3 . Fig. 1 shows the dependence of E_{corr} on NaN_3 concentration. As can be seen, E_{corr} increases linearly with logarithm of NaN_3 over the concentration range 10^{-4} to $10^{-1}M$. The slopes in 1.0 and 0.1 N H_2SO_4 solutions are 25 ± 2 and 26 ± 2 mV/decade respectively. On the other hand, the slopes of E_{corr} vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$ relations in absence and presence of NaN_3 are 60 and 52 mV/decade respectively. These slopes are within the range of those reported in HCl, HClO_4 and H_2SO_4 solutions; $dE_{\text{corr}}/d \text{pH} = -51$ to 70 mV/decade^{10,14,17,19}.

The steady anodic and cathodic polarisation curves for mild steel in deoxygenated 1.0 and 0.1 N H_2SO_4 solutions in absence and presence of xM NaN_3 ($x=10^{-5}$ - $10^{-1}M$) were recorded. In all cases the potential was changed in the cathodic

Fig. 1. Plots of E_{corr} vs $\log \text{NaN}_3$ concentration for iron in: (O) 1.0 N and (x) 0.1 N H_2SO_4 ; horizontal arrows refer to E_{corr} values in absence of NaN_3 .

Fig. 2. Potentiostatic polarisation curves of iron in deoxygenated 1.0 N H_2SO_4 in absence and presence of NaN_3 of different concentrations: (O) 0.1 M , (Δ) 0.01 M , (x) 0.001 M and (●) blank.

direction from the corrosion potential and the electrode was left to attain the corrosion potential before the change of the potential in the anodic direction. A typical example for the polarisation curves in 1.0 N H_2SO_4 is shown in Fig. 2. As can be seen, the presence of NaN_3 affects the cathodic branches of the polarisation curves much more than the anodic ones and shifts them in the more active direction. In absence and presence of NaN_3 , the slopes of the cathodic and anodic

Tafel lines, b_c and b_a are nearly the same, $b_c = 122 \pm 2$ and $b_a = 31 \pm 2$ mV/decade. The deviation of both cathodic and anodic curves from the linear Tafel behaviour at high current densities is connected to the ohmic resistance and the concentration polarisations^{16,28}.

The b_c values are in fair agreement with those usually reported for the hydrogen evolution reaction on iron in acid solutions^{10,16,28}. The b_a values equal to those reported by Lorenz³ in 0.5 N H_2SO_4 , $b_a = 30$ mV/decade and Hurlen¹³ in 1 N HCl , $b_a = 30$ mV/decade.

The corrosion current (i_{corr}) was determined by extrapolation of the cathodic or anodic branches to the current density corresponding to the corrosion potential^{16,28}. The corrosion currents and Tafel slopes are given in Table 1. Figs. 3 and 4 show the dependence of the cathodic current at constant potential and the corrosion current on NaN_3 concentration. The orders of the cathodic reaction with respect to NaN_3 , $d \log i_c / d \log C$, in 1.0 and 0.1 N H_2SO_4 are 1 and 0.45, respectively. In absence of NaN_3 , the order of reaction with respect to H^+ ion concentration, $d \log i_c / d \log [\text{H}^+] = 1$, agrees well with the reported data^{10,20,28}. In presence of NaN_3 , the order is 0.55. The values of $d \log i_{\text{corr}} / d \log C$ in 1.0 and 0.1 N H_2SO_4 are 1 and 0.5, respectively.

TABLE 1—CORROSION CURRENTS AND POTENTIALS AND TAFEL SLOPES FOR MILD STEEL IN SULPHURIC ACID SOLUTIONS CONTAINING NaN_3 AT 25°

H_2SO_4 N	$[\text{NaN}_3]$ M	$-E_{\text{corr}}$ mV	b_c mV	b_a mV	* i_{corr} mV
1.0	0	480	121	30	0.085
	10^{-3}	460	122	32	0.123
	10^{-2}	435	124	32	1.05
	10^{-1}	407	124	31	11.00
0.1	0	540	120	30	0.050
	10^{-5}	535	121	31	0.061
	10^{-4}	525	122	31	0.100
	10^{-3}	510	123	32	0.210
	10^{-2}	487	124	32	0.450

*The values are given per apparent electrode area (= 0.25 cm^2).

Fig. 5 shows the effect of NaN_3 on the anodic polarisation behaviour of mild steel in 1.0 N H_2SO_4 . As can be seen, both the active-passive transition and the passivation regions are affected by the presence of NaN_3 . The dependence of the maximum current in the active-passive transition (i_M) and the passivation current (i_p) on NaN_3 concentration are shown in Fig. 6. The presence of NaN_3 upto 0.1 M did not result in pitting corrosion.

Fig 5

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log i_c$ vs $\log \text{NaN}_3$ concentration for iron in: (O) 1.0 N ($E = 550$ mV) and (x) 0.1 N H_2SO_4 ($E = 600$ mV).

Fig. 4. Plots of $\log i_{\text{corr}}$ vs $\log \text{NaN}_3$ concentration for iron in: (O) 1.0 N and (x) 0.1 N H_2SO_4 ; horizontal arrows refer to corrosion currents in absence of NaN_3 .

In strong acid solutions, the azide species are mostly found as hydrazoic acid, HN_3^{21} .

HN_3 is involved in the following redox reactions (21),

Fig. 5. Potentiostatic anodic polarisation curves of iron in deoxygenated 1.0 N H_2SO_4 in absence and presence of NaN_3 of different concentrations; (O) 0.1 M, (Δ) 0.01 M, (x) 0.001 M and (.) blank.

Fig. 6. Plots of i_p and i_m on $\log \text{NaN}_3$ concentration for iron in: 1.0 N H_2SO_4 ; horizontal arrows refer to the values in absence of NaN_3 .

The above equilibria show that HN_3 could decompose thermodynamically in acid solutions to N_2 at potentials more positive to -2.8 V while it could decompose to NH_4^+ ions and N_2 or NH_4^+ ions at potentials less positive to 1.82 or 0.66 V, respectively. Within the potential range and the experimental conditions used in the present study, the three redox reactions (2-4) could occur.

The observed increase in i_{corr} with increase of NaN_3 concentration as well as the great effect of NaN_3 on the cathodic polarisation curves rather than the anodic ones, can be explained by assuming the reduction of HN_3 beside the hydrogen evolution as the cathodic reactions and the dissolution

of iron as the anodic reaction. According to equation (4), the dependence of the potential on HN_3 concentration at constant hydrogen ion and nitrogen concentrations is given by

$$E = E^\circ + \frac{0.059}{2} \log [\text{HN}_3] + \text{constant} \quad (5)$$

The theoretical $dE/d \log [\text{HN}_3]$ is 29.5 mV/decade which is close to the experimental value (26 mV/decade). The experimental $dE/d \log [\text{H}^+] = 52$ mV/decade is far from the theoretical values for the equilibria (3) and (4), i.e. 81 and 85.5 mV/decade respectively. The experimental value seems to be closer to the theoretical value of H_2/H^+ system, $dE/d \log [\text{H}^+] = 59$ mV/decade. However, E_{corr} shifts in presence of NaN_3 to more positive values in the direction of potentials of the equilibria (3) and (4). On the other hand, the dependence of the order of reaction of the medium acidity, $d \log i_c/d \log [\text{HN}_3]$ in 1.0 and 0.1 N H_2SO_4 are 1 and 0.45, seems to reflect the dependence of the reducible azide species concentration on pH. It is also in consistence with the fact that HN_3 reduction depends on H^+ ion concentration as indicated in equations (3) and (4).

The present study shows that the azide ions behave as accelerators for corrosion of mild steel in acid solutions. This is not in contradiction with the previously reported corrosion inhibition properties of the azide ions^{26,27} because the inhibition of azide ions occurs only in neutral and alkaline solutions. In strong acid solutions, azide ions are mostly found as HN_3 and it seems that both reduction of HN_3 (most probably via equation 4) and hydrogen evolution reactions predominate at the cathodic reactions during corrosion and cathodic polarisation of mild steel in sulphuric acid solutions. Both are two-electron transfer reactions with $b_c = 120$ mV/decade as observed experimentally.

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